

YOGA AS A PART OF UG CURRICULUM

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ABSTRACT

Yoga is an ancient science to strengthen the Physical and Mental ability. It was practicing since from 6000 years in India and currently close to 18 million people all around the world are enjoying its health care benefits. The popularity of yoga has been increasing rapidly across the globe because of its safety, affordability and ability to manage physical and mental disorders. Higher education involves young generation of the age group 18-25 years. Higher Education policies and Curriculum are trying to achieve their best in the field of teaching learning, research and extension activities, but due to modernization of the world, distraction among the younger generation is more. Actually they are living in a physically inactive world, hence they have to be motivated and accelerated by adopting Yoga as one of the subject in their curriculum.

Key words: Yoga, 18-25years, Higher education, Curriculum.

INTRODUCTION:

Education has many purposes; the important ones may be described as to acquire knowledge, skill, reasoning ability, systematic analysis of the concerned subject they study. Education has to help the student to understand the facts about the subject in broader sense. Education must help the students to know about the moral implication of action and choice they make. Education has to improve communication skills and to develop questioning ability. Education must develop good culture and habits among the young generation.

The aim of the education can be attained through curriculum. “Curriculum is all of the activities that are to be achieved for a certain period”. In the broader sense “the curriculum is a planned activity which is designed to implement a particular educational aim”. Set of such aims in terms of context; are what is to be taught?, how much and what amount of knowledge to be taught, what are the types of skills to be taught and which types of attitudes to be developed among the students for their well beingness.

Coming to Higher education curriculum, it is a dynamic curriculum with necessary addition and changes introduced from time to time by the universities with a prime objective to maintain updated curriculum and also providing their inputs to cater the needs of the students for their development. There is an increased pressure in higher education system to equip students with not only the expertise derived from traditionalist also to give students sufficient range of skills to empower them to play effective role in concerned jobs. The thrust of education is shifting to market based one, on the changing philosophy from idealism to pragmatism. The institution of higher education need to have clear understanding of what they are seeking to achieve through their curricular offerings, research and extension programmes.¹

Science and Technology helping us make our lives easier and comfortable. Because of the advancement in communication system, transportation facility etc., we stopped moving from place to place, it appears that the

whole world is living in a physically inactive state. Students are busy with the mobiles, videogames, learning computers, in their leisure hours. Students are not interested in playing outdoor games and sports, all these facts make them restless, passive, indifferent, incurious, disinterested and rude. These attitudes of the students results in failure to reach the goal of the education.

Thus there is an urgent need to bring about a positive change in the present day students life styles by introducing certain aspects which help to make the youngsters humble, curious, to develop a growth mind set, obedient and peaceful. These factors can be achieved by introducing Yoga as one of the aspect in their curriculum.

Historical Importance of Yoga

Yogais an ancient practice, which improves the physical and mental health.²It helps to achieve the balance between individual personality and rest of the universe. In *Bhagavadgeetha*the yoga has been described as

Endowed with the wisdom of evenness of mind, one can cast off in this life both good deeds and evil deeds;therefore devote yourself to Yoga, skill in action is Yoga

The scientific research has shown that the relaxed state in Yoga is accompanied by changes in physiological parameters related to stress. The parameters include respiration and oxygen consumption, blood pressure and heart rate, brain function, blood flow, secretion of hormones, muscle tone, strength and flexibility and biological age.³The regular practice of Yoga reduces mental stress and improves the autonomic response leading to the prevention and management of cardiovascular diseases.⁴ Another study revealed that six week Yoga training improved thermoregulatory efficiency as measured by weight loss response.⁵The literature survey reveals that yoga is harmless, inexpensive and able to manage the chronic disorders.

Yoga can be introduced as one of the part of Physical education up to school level, from high school onwards higher levels of yoga can be adopted. In Universities and Colleges the advanced aspect of yoga in the form of training, treatment and research is to be introduced. It can be introduced as mind culture and as spiritual culture in colleges and at university level.

Recently a team of 500 doctors in United States of America made a research on Surya Namaskaraand its benefits. Almost all the participants are of the opinion that yoga is one of the safest and inexpensive fitness regime, then why not for our students.

So, yoga must be a part of curriculum then it will become part of education. As students in pursuit of higher education have enhanced level of understanding, yoga must become part of pedagogy. It is at this level of education that an individual starts viewing “Big picture of Life”. A reformed body through yoga can bring harmony between body and mind and make a person complete in all respects. If we introduce yoga in curriculum of higher education of course there will be change in the attitude of our youth which definitely improves the quality of our society and this holistic change definitely results in the progress of our nation.

With the above information I would like to suggest for implementing yoga in our undergraduate curriculum as one of the important subject.

CONCLUSION:

The purpose of education is not to produce mere scholars, technician and job hunters, but to produce human beings who have the capacity of understanding the life and collective problems. The regular practice of yoga reduces mental stress and improves the physical and mental health conditions which are useful to develop the personality in a positive way. Yoga is economical, affordable to all. Hence we suggest implementing yoga education in the curriculum to have strong, well-built, well cultured studentcommunityfor the betterment of our nation.

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